

ALGORITHMIC APPROACH TO SOLVING MULTIPLE INTEGRALS

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Abstract

The idea of our work is showing the fastest and easiest methods for solving problems such as calculating area and volume using double and triple integrals. These are the most difficult topics of mathematical analysis and many students do not reach these paragraphs, and in order to simplify, we have made these algorithms and methods.

Also, these methods of solving are given in algorithmic way, which is convenient to remember. In addition, formulas are given in table form, which shows that formulas are connected with each other and it's as well easy to remember.

Keywords: multiple integral, area, volume, integral problems, calculus, algorithmic approach.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background info

Firstly, let's define what is integral. Integration is the calculation of the antiderivative of a function. That is, the derivative of the computed function by integration is the primary function. In other words, the tangent line of the calculated function by integration is the primary function. Also, the function obtained by integration can express the area under the curve of the graph of the function. That's for finding area or volume of objects we can use a definite multiple integral. A limit of Riemann sums is the definite integral of a continuous function $f(x)$ over the interval $[a, b]$. And integral of a function with more than one variable is called a multiple integral.

The concept of integral appeared somewhere around 2000 years ago in ancient Egypt. At that time, the integral was calculated by one of the most complicated methods. They broke the figure, whose volume or area they wanted to find, into an infinite number of parts, whose volumes or areas were already known. It was very hard to calculate and takes a lot of time. Since that time, the method of finding the integral has developed and reached the method that we all know, that is, finding the integral using formulas. By the way, this method was first invented by Arab scientists. Or rather, it was introduced to the world for the first time by Abu Ali al-Hasan ibn al-Hassan ibn al-Haytham al-Basri.

1.2 Literature review

We have researched more than 20 books to compare methods of solving examples. We found some shortcomings in these books, which we will write about in the next paragraph.

In 10 books that used the same method of solving integrals and this is a horizontal solution method. We have identified the main 5 among them, since our work is more focused on computer science and engineers.

1.3 Research questions/research gap

Let's consider examples that are given in fairly popular books in our field:

In [1] on page 316 it is not shown what was obtained after integration before setting the boundaries and it is not shown how the boundaries of the integrals were calculated.

In [2] on page 178 there is too short explanation and it is not shown how the boundaries of the integrals were calculated too.

In [3] on page 17 the upper and lower boundaries are not indicated and it is not shown how the boundaries of the integrals were calculated too.

In books [4] on page 880 and [5] on page 53 no full solution are given at the end of example. Also, formulas mass and first moments we gave in table form which is more convenient than in ordinary form, like in this book. And we can see the connection between formulas in table form, but here in this book they don't seem to be related.

In [6]-[10] given the horizontal method of solution, which is too long for calculating.

These omissions quite strongly affect the ease of understanding information, even lead to a loss of learning motivation.

2.1 Triple Integrals in Rectangular Coordinates

DEFINITION $V = \iiint_D dV$	The volume of a closed, bounded region D in space is
DEFINITION Average value of F over $D = \frac{1}{\text{volume of } D} \iiint_D F dV$	The average value of a function F over a region D in space is defined by the formula

Examples: №(2.1-2.4)- Calculate the volume of a body bounded by given surfaces:*Algorithm:***1 - Draw a graph**

2 - Set indexes to known functions using graph(The point(or function) that is lower(less) is the first one(x_1, y_1, z_1)). Find the remaining functions(or intersection points) using the equations that are given and also set indexes using graph.

3 - Using the indexed functions(or intersection points), you need to set the limits of integration in the triple integral $V = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \int_{z_1}^{z_2} dz dy dx$ and solve it.

Example(№2.1)

$$z = x^2 + y^2; \quad x + y = 2; \quad x \geq 0; \quad y \geq 0; \quad z \geq 0$$

Solution:

$$z_2 = x^2 + y^2; \quad x + y_2 = 2; \quad x_1 \geq 0; \quad y_1 \geq 0; \quad z_1 \geq 0$$

$$y_2 = 2 - x$$

$$y_1 = y_2$$

$$0 = 2 - x$$

$$x_2 = 2$$

Figure 2.1.1 (3D graph of Example №2.1)

Figure 2.1.2 (2D graph of Example №2.1)

$$\begin{aligned} V &= \int_0^2 \left(\int_0^{2-x} \left(\int_0^{x^2+y^2} dz \right) dy \right) dx = \int_0^2 \left(\int_0^{2-x} (x^2 + y^2) dy \right) dx = \\ &= \int_0^2 \left(x^2 y + \frac{y^3}{3} \right) \Big|_0^{2-x} dx = \int_0^2 \left(2x^2 - x^3 + \frac{(2-x)^3}{3} \right) dx = \end{aligned}$$

(Variant 1):

$$\begin{aligned} &= \int_0^2 \left(2x^2 - x^3 + \frac{8 - 12x + 6x^2 - x^3}{3} \right) dx = \\ &= \int_0^2 \left(-\frac{4x^3}{3} + 4x^2 - 4x + \frac{8}{3} \right) dx = \left(-\frac{x^4}{3} + \frac{4x^3}{3} - 2x^2 + \frac{8x}{3} \right) \Big|_0^2 = \\ &= -\frac{16}{3} + \frac{32}{3} - 8 + \frac{16}{3} = \frac{-16 + 32 - 24 + 16}{3} = \frac{8}{3} \end{aligned}$$

(Variant 2):

$$\begin{aligned} &= \int_0^2 (2x^2 - x^3) dx - \int_0^2 \frac{(2-x)^3}{3} d(2-x) = \\ &= \left(\frac{2x^3}{3} - \frac{x^4}{4} - \frac{(2-x)^4}{12} \right) \Big|_0^2 = \frac{16}{3} - 4 + \frac{16}{12} = \\ &= \frac{64 - 48 + 16}{12} = \frac{32}{12} = \frac{8}{3} \end{aligned}$$

Additional explanation:

In Example №2.1 by algorithm, which is given above, we firstly drew graphs (Figure 2.1.1 and Figure 2.1.2). Looking at the graphs, we indexed known functions(i.e., x_1, y_1, z_1, z_2), as mentioned in algorithm we set index 1 to point(or function) that is lower(less), and set index 2 to point(or function) that is upper(more).

We found y_2 by subtracting x from both sides of equation ($x + y = 2$). As we know y_1 and y_2 , we equalized them, and found x_2 by adding x to both sides of equation ($0 = 2 - x$). Then we set limits of integration in the triple integral and solved it. In the solution we show 2 variants of solving, Variant 1 was solved by just opening

brackets using abbreviated multiplication formula $(a + b)^3 = a^3 + 3a^2b + 3ab^2 + b^3$. Variant 2 was solved by change of variables. That's we changed variable of integration to $(2 - x)$ from x , and multiplied the function to -1 , because derivative of $(2 - x)$ is -1 .

Example(№2.2)

$$z = x^2; x - 2y + 4 = 0; x + y - 5 = 0; z \geq 0$$

Solution:

$$z_2 = x^2; x - 2y_1 + 4 = 0; x + y_2 - 5 = 0; z_1 \geq 0$$

$$z_2 = z_1 - 2y_1 = -4 - x \quad y_2 = 5 - x$$

$$x_1 = 0 \quad y_1 = 2 + \frac{x}{2}$$

$$y_1 = y_2$$

$$2 + \frac{x}{2} = 5 - x$$

$$\frac{3x}{2} = 3$$

$$x_2 = 2$$

Figure 2.1.3 (3D graph of Example №2.2)

Figure 2.1.4 (2D graph of Example №2.2)

$$\begin{aligned} V &= \int_0^2 \int_{\frac{x}{2}+2}^{5-x} \int_0^{x^2} dz dy dx = \int_0^2 \int_{\frac{x}{2}+2}^{5-x} x^2 dy dx = \int_0^2 (x^2 y) \Big|_{\frac{x}{2}+2}^{5-x} dx = \\ &= \int_0^2 \left(5x^2 - x^3 - \frac{x^3}{2} - 2x^2 \right) dx = \int_0^2 \left(-\frac{3x^3}{2} + 3x^2 \right) dx = \left(-\frac{3x^4}{8} + x^3 \right) \Big|_0^2 = \\ &= -\frac{3 \cdot 16}{8} + 8 = -6 + 8 = 2 \end{aligned}$$

Additional explanation:

In Example №2.2 by algorithm, which is given above, we firstly drew graphs (Figure 2.1.3 and Figure 2.1.4). Looking at the graphs, we indexed known functions z_1 and z_2 , as mentioned in algorithm we set index 1 to point(or function) that is lower(less), and set index 2 to point(or function) that is upper(more).

By equalizing z_1 and z_2 , we found x_1 . Then using equations, that are given we found y_1 and y_2 . After that, by equalizing them, i.e., y_1 and y_2 , we found x_2 . By third step of algorithm, we set limits of integration to triple integral and solved it.

Example(№2.3)

$$z = 4x^2 + y^2; y = x; y = 2x; x = 1; z \geq 0$$

Solution:

$$z_2 = 4x^2 + y^2; y_1 = x; y_2 = 2x; x_2 = 1; z_1 \geq 0$$

$$y_1 = y_2$$

$$x = 2x$$

$$2x - x = 0$$

$$x_1 = 0$$

Figure 2.1.5 (3D graph of Example №2.3)

Figure 2.1.6 (2D graph of Example №2.3)

$$\begin{aligned}
 V &= \int_0^1 \int_x^{2x} \int_0^{4x^2+y^2} dz dy dx = \int_0^1 \int_x^{2x} (4x^2 + y^2) dy dx = \\
 &= \int_0^1 \left(4x^2 y + \frac{y^3}{3} \right) \Big|_x^{2x} dx = \int_0^1 \left(8x^3 \cdot \frac{1}{3} + \frac{8}{3} x^3 - 4x^3 - \frac{x^3}{3} \right) dx = \\
 &= \int_0^1 \frac{24 + 8 - 12 - 1}{3} x^3 dx = \int_0^1 \frac{19}{3} x^3 dx = \frac{19x^4}{12} \Big|_0^1 = \frac{76}{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

Additional explanation:

In Example №2.3 by algorithm, which is given above, firstly, we drew graphs (Figure 2.1.5 and Figure 2.1.6). Looking at the graphs, we indexed known functions (x_2, y_1, y_2, z_1, z_2), as mentioned in algorithm we set index 1 to function (or point) that is lower(less), and set index 2 to function (or point) that is upper(more).

We equalized y_1 and y_2 . By this, we found x_1 . And after finding and indexing all functions, we did third step of algorithm, that is set limits of integration to triple integral and solved it.

Example(№2.4)

$$y = \sqrt{x}; y = 2x; x + y + z = 1; z \geq 0$$

Solution:

$$\begin{aligned}
 y_2 &= \sqrt{x}; y_1 = 2x; x + y + z = 1; z_1 \geq 0 \\
 y_2 &= y_1 \quad z_2 = 1 - x - y \\
 \sqrt{x} &= 2x \\
 \sqrt{x} - 2x &= 0 \\
 \sqrt{x}(2 - \sqrt{x}) &= 0 \\
 \sqrt{x_1} &= 0 \quad \sqrt{x_2} = 2 \\
 x_1 &= 0 \quad x_2 = 4
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2.1.7 (3D graph of Example №2.4)

Figure 2.1.8 (2D graph of Example №2.4)

$$\begin{aligned}
 V &= \int_0^4 \int_{2x}^{\sqrt{x}} \int_0^{1-x-y} dz dy dx = \int_0^4 \int_{2x}^{\sqrt{x}} (1-x-y) dy dx = \\
 &= \int_0^4 \left(y - xy - \frac{y^2}{2} \right) \Big|_{2x}^{\sqrt{x}} dx = \int_0^4 \left(\sqrt{x} - x\sqrt{x} - \frac{x}{2} - 2x + 2x^2 + 2x^2 \right) dx = \\
 &= \int_0^4 \left(4x^2 - x\sqrt{x} - \frac{5x}{2} + \sqrt{x} \right) dx = \left(\frac{4x^3}{3} - \frac{2x^{\frac{5}{2}}}{5} - \frac{5x^2}{4} + \frac{2x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{3} \right) \Big|_0^4 = \\
 &= \frac{256^{\frac{5}{3}}}{3} - \frac{64^{\frac{3}{5}}}{5} - 20^{\frac{15}{5}} + \frac{16^{\frac{5}{3}}}{3} = \frac{1280 - 192 - 300 + 80}{15} = \frac{868}{15}
 \end{aligned}$$

Additional explanation:

In Example №2.4 by algorithm, which is given above, as mentioned in first step we drew graphs (Figure 2.1.7 and Figure 2.1.8). Looking at the graphs, we indexed known functions (y_1, y_2, z_1) , as stated in algorithm we set index 1 to point(or function) that is lower(less), and set index 2 to point(or function) that is upper(more).

By using equation that is given, we found z_2 . Then, by equalizing y_1 and y_2 , we easily found x_1 and x_2 . After that, we did third step of algorithm, i.e., using functions, which we found and indexed above, set limits of integration to triple integral and solved it.

SELF-STUDY №2.1 (Answers are given above self-study №2.2)

Calculate the volume of a body bounded by given surfaces:

1. $z = \frac{x^2}{2} + y^2, x + y = 3, x \geq 0, y \geq 0, z \geq 0$
2. $5x + 3y - 15 = 0, 5z = y^2, x \geq 0, y \geq 0, z \geq 0$
3. $z = x^2, x + y = 2, y = x, x = 0, z \geq 0$

Examples №(2.5-2.8) Set the limits of integration in the triple integral $\iiint_V w(x, y, z) dx dy dz$ if the region V is bounded by the specified surfaces. Draw the integration area.

Algorithm:

1 - Draw a graph

2 - Set indexes to known functions using graph(The point(or function) that is lower(less) is the first one(x_1, y_1, z_1)). Find the remaining functions(or intersection points) using the equations that are given and also set indexes using graph.

3 - Using the indexed functions(or intersection points), you need to set the limits of integration in the triple integral $\int_{x_1}^{x_2} \int_{y_1}^{y_2} \int_{z_1}^{z_2} w(x, y, z) dz dy dx$

Example(№2.5)

$$V: x = 2; y = 4x; y = 5\sqrt{x}; z \geq 0; z = 3$$

Solution:

$$V: x_4 = 2; y_1 = 4x; y_2 = 5\sqrt{x}; z_1 \geq 0; z_2 = 3$$

$$y_1 = y_2$$

$$4x = 5\sqrt{x}$$

$$4x - 5\sqrt{x} = 0$$

$$\sqrt{x}(4\sqrt{x} - 5) = 0$$

$$\sqrt{x_1} = 0 \quad 4\sqrt{x_2} - 5 = 0$$

$$x_1 = 0 \quad \sqrt{x_2} = \frac{5}{4}$$

$$x_2 = \frac{25}{16}$$

$$x_3 = x_2 = \frac{25}{16}; y_3 = y_2 = 5\sqrt{x}; y_4 = y_1 = 4x; z_3 = z_1 \geq 0; z_4 = z_2 = 3$$

Figure 2.1.9 (3D graph of Example №2.5)

Figure 2.1.10 (2D graph of Example №2.5)

$$\iiint_V w(x, y, z) dz dy dx = \int_0^{\frac{25}{16}} \int_{4x}^{5\sqrt{x}} \int_0^5 w(x, y, z) dz dy dx + \int_{\frac{25}{16}}^2 \int_{5\sqrt{x}}^{4x} \int_0^5 w(x, y, z) dz dy dx$$

Additional explanation:

In Example №2.5 by algorithm, which is given above, we firstly drew graphs (Figure 2.1.9 and Figure 2.1.10). Looking at the graphs, we can notice that we have two regions (V_1 and V_2), i.e., we should set limits of integration to two integrals. Also, we indexed known functions (x_4, y_1, y_2, z_1, z_2). After that, we found x_1 and x_2 by equalizing y_1 and y_2 . In graph, we see that both regions bounded by same functions in z -axis and that upper limit functions of first region V_1 is the lower limit functions of second region V_2 . So, by using graph and founded functions, we indexed remaining functions (x_3, y_3, y_4, z_3, z_4). Then we did last step, that is set limits to triple integrals.

Example(№2.6)

$$V: x = 2; y = 3x; z \geq 0; z = \sqrt{5y}$$

Solution:

$$V: x_2 = 2; y_2 = 3x; z_1 \geq 0; z_2 = \sqrt{5y}$$

$$\begin{aligned} z_1 &= z_2 \\ 0 &= \sqrt{5y} \\ y_1 &= 0 \\ y_2 &= y_1 \\ 3x &= 0 \\ x_1 &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2.1.11 (3D graph of Example №2.6)

Figure 2.1.12 (2D graph of Example №2.6)

$$\iiint_V w(x, y, z) dz dy dx = \int_0^2 \int_0^{3x} \int_0^{\sqrt{5y}} w(x, y, z) dz dy dx$$

Additional explanation:

In Example №2.6 by above given algorithm's first step we drew graphs (Figure 2.1.11 and Figure 2.1.12). Looking at the drawn graphs, we indexed known functions (x_2, y_2, z_1, z_2) , as stated in algorithm we set index 1 to point(or function) that is lower(less), and set index 2 to point(or function) that is upper(more).

By equalizing functions z_1 and z_2 we found y_1 . As we have y_1 and y_2 , we equalized them and took x_1 . So, after ending second step, we went to do the last step. That is using indexed functions(points) that we derive, we set the limits of integration in the triple integral.

Example(№2.7)

$$V: x \geq 0; y = 4x; y = 2; z \geq 0; x + y + z = 5$$

Solution:

$$V: x_1 \geq 0; y_1 = 4x; y_2 = 2; z_1 \geq 0; x + y + z = 5$$

$$y_1 = y_2 \quad z_2 = 5 - y - x$$

$$4x = 2 \quad z_1 = z_2$$

$$x_2 = 0.5 \quad 0 = 5 - y - x$$

$$y_6 = 5 - x$$

$$y_2 = y_6 \quad y_1 = y_6$$

$$2 = 5 - x \quad 4x = 5 - x$$

$$x_6 = 3 \quad 5x = 5$$

$$x_4 = x_5 = 1$$

$$x_3 = x_2 = 0.5; y_5 = y_3 = y_2 = 2; y_4 = y_1 = 4x; z_5 = z_3 = z_1;$$

$$z_6 = z_4 = z_2$$

Figure 2.1.13 (3D graph of Example №2.7)

Figure 2.1.14 (2D graph of Example №2.7)

$$\begin{aligned} \iiint_V w(x, y, z) dz dy dx &= \int_0^{0.5} \int_{4x}^2 \int_0^{5-y-x} w(x, y, z) dz dy dx + \\ &+ \int_{0.5}^1 \int_2^{4x} \int_0^{5-y-x} w(x, y, z) dz dy dx + \int_1^3 \int_2^{5-x} \int_0^{5-y-x} w(x, y, z) dz dy dx \end{aligned}$$

Additional explanation:

In Example №2.7 by above stated algorithm's first step we drew graphs (Figure 2.1.13 and Figure 2.1.14). Looking at the drawn 2D and 3D graphs, we can mention that we deal with three regions(V_1, V_2 and V_3), so we should set limits of integration to three triple integrals. Here, V_2 and V_3 we took as two different regions, which divides by line $x = 1$. Note that we set odd(1, 3, 5) indexes to point(or function) that is lower(less), and set even(2, 4, 6) indexes to point(or function) that is upper(more).

We indexed known functions (x_1, y_1, y_2, z_1) and using equation that is given easily found z_2 . After that we equalized z_1 and z_2 , by this we found y_6 . Then by equalizing y_1 and y_2 , y_2 and y_6 , y_1 and y_6 we found x_2, x_6 and x_5 . By looking at the graphs, we easily understand that some boundary functions of regions are equal, i.e., we found rest of limit functions $(x_3, x_4, y_3, y_4, y_5, z_3, z_4, z_5, z_6)$

Example(№2.8)

$$V: x = 4; y = \frac{x}{4}; y \geq 0; z \geq 0; z = x^2 + 4y^2$$

Solution:

$$V: x_2 = 4; y_2 = \frac{x}{4}; y_1 \geq 0; z_1 \geq 0; z_2 = x^2 + 4y^2$$

Figure 2.1.15 (3D graph of Example №2.8)

Figure 2.1.16 (2D graph of Example №2.8)

$$\iiint_V w(x, y, z) dz dy dx = \int_0^4 \int_0^{\frac{x}{4}} \int_0^{x^2+4y^2} w(x, y, z) dz dy dx$$

Additional explanation:

In Example №2.8 by above stated algorithm, firstly, we drew graphs (Figure 2.1.15 and Figure 2.1.16). Looking at the drawn 2D and 3D, we indexed known functions $(x_2, y_1, y_2, z_1, z_2)$, as stated in algorithm we set index 1 to point(or function) that is lower(less), and set index 2 to point(or function) that is upper(more). So, we had to find only x_1 . For this, we equalized y_1 and y_2 . When we found and indexed all boundary functions, we should do third step. That is, we just set limits of integration to the triple integral.

Answers for self-study №2.1: 1) $\frac{81}{8}$; 2) $\frac{25}{4}$; 3) $\frac{1}{6}$

SELF-STUDY №2.2

Set the limits of integration in the triple integral $\iiint_V w(x, y, z) dx dy dz$ if the region V is bounded by the specified surfaces. Draw the integration area.

1. $V: x = 2, y = \frac{1}{2}x, y \geq 0, z \geq 0, z = \frac{1}{2}(x^2 + y^2)$

2. $V: x \geq 0, y = 2x, y = 2, z \geq 0, z = 2(x^2 + y^2)$

3. $V: x \geq 0, y = 4x, y = 8, z \geq 0, z = x^2 + y^2$

Answers for self-study №2.2: 1) $\int_0^2 \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}x} \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}(x^2 + y^2)} w(x, y, z) dz dy dx$;

2) $\int_0^1 \int_{2x}^2 \int_0^{2(x^2 + y^2)} w(x, y, z) dz dy dx$; 3) $\int_0^2 \int_{4x}^8 \int_0^{x^2 + y^2} w(x, y, z) dz dy dx$
(solutions of self-studies are given at the end of section 3.3)

Conclusion

Methods for solving problems about Multiple Integrals are provided that are accessible to the concept and take less time to solve. It should be mindful of that these topics are very important and are applied in many areas. For example, in astronomy (movement of stars), medicine (computerized tomography), construction (area and volume), etc. It should be noted that an algorithmic approach to providing information was used. When solving problems, the tabular form helps to better understand the material and shows how much easier it is to solve one or another example in another form. Graphs (was plotted by [11], [12]) are integral, so capturing each task with graphs helps present the example in an abstract way. Our work will be useful to engineers and mathematicians in the initial stages, which will allow them to create a solid foundation.

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